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Motivation and Its Impact on Employee Performance

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ABSTRACT

For many businesses, motivation is a crucial problem that may aid in the development of both individuals and organizations. The motivation of the workforce has always been and always will be a crucial factor in attaining success and the goals of a firm. The present study has been carried out to find out the impact of motivation on employee performance and to study the types of motivation given to the employees. For this purpose, the researcher has selected 25 private employees following the random sampling method. A four-point likert scale was used to evaluate the results of each question that the respondent responded in the questionnaire and interview that were used to gather the data. The data were tabulated and cross tabulated using SPSS statistical software. Findings of the study indicate that motivation, which may be either monetary or non-monetary, is a key factor in any organization's performance and there is significant relationship between the motivation and the performance of the employees. The study's conclusions showed that motivation increases organizational productivity in addition to raising staff morale.

INTRODUCTION

Every organization, whether it is public or private, needs to consider motivation. For the success of any organization motivation play an important role. 2004, Zameer *et al.* Employees' drive to fulfill their esteem, physiological safety, social safety, psychological level, and self actualization level directly affects them. (Maslow). An organization has objectives that can only be met via the efforts of the individuals who work there. Individuals have their own "goals" in life, which are probably distinct from the organization's aims. Getting people to work in a manner that the organization accomplishes its objectives, or the need for employee motivation, is a key issue for management.

The level of devotion people have to their work is referred to as motivation. Workplace motivation is concerned with loyalty to a company, its goals, and aims. Including Dave Needham (2003). An individual's or a group's motivation may be both good and bad. The motivation of workers should be enhanced and attained, according to several authors on organizational and management theory, either by managerial action or through organizational structure. The behavioural school of management thinking is linked to a lot of research; however motivational theories are not limited to "behaviourists."

Motivation is fundamentally meant to facilitate behavioural alteration. It is a force that enables people to move in the direction of certain goals (Shahzadi *et al.*,2014). According to a research on employee motivation by Grant (2008), as referenced in Irum (2014), motivation drove outcomes including productivity, performance, and perseverance. The phrase "motivation" is a generic one that encompasses all types of drive, wants, desires, and similar factors. When a manager "motivates" their team members, they are acting in a way that they think will

fulfil the team members' needs and wants and lead to the desired behavior (Wehrich *et al.*,2008).

Background of the Study

Robbinson *et al.* (2007) made the assumption that it is more important to understand the variables that inspire workers than it is to ask if a person is motivated or not. Since they believe that the issue is not whether a person is motivated or not, it is still unclear how motivation should be instilled in the workforce. The motivation of those workers must be the main focus of management efforts if they want to see increased levels of productivity and behaviour on the job, since human resources are a company's most precious asset. DeCenzo *et al.* emphasize the motivation function's objective in their paper, which is to create an environment that encourages and supports the talented, knowledgeable, competent, and informed staff to exert greater effort toward attaining the organization's goals. The study's findings provide insight into the relationship between employee motivation and productivity as well as the factors that support employee motivation. There aren't many important concepts accessible for understanding what factors affect motivation. Three of these theories are the Herzberg two-factor theory, Fredrick Taylor's theory, and Abraham Maslow's theory.

LITERATURE REVIEW

(Mustapha, 2020) discovered that motivated workers outperform those who are not. Motivation may raise employee performance. The investigation's findings demonstrate that several public and private schools in Talata Mafara implement critical strategies to encourage their staff, including training, promotion, welfare services, and a positive working connection.

(Wael, 2021) analyses how employee performance is

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impacted by motivation. A quantitative approach is used, including the use of questionnaires, interviews, and data collection methods. A Likert Scale was chosen as the main data collection instrument, and staff members answered to a distributed questionnaire. The major findings demonstrate that motivational factors considerably enhance worker performance. As a result, high employee performance and motivation are associated. This research also discusses the value of an ethical code in carrying out a reliable motivating mode. The work's ramifications highlight the need of improving employee performance via incentive, free from prejudice or discrimination.

(Nabi *et al.*,2017) The heart of every company is its employees. Collaboration among employees is a must for any business to operate smoothly and without hiccups. Along with a great working relationship with the organizations top management, it is critical for employees to have good connections with their coworkers. The research that follows is a self-conducted examination of the advantages of employee performance-improving tools. The study also focused on elements that diminish worker motivation and have a detrimental effect on output. To gather primary data, a sample of people was chosen and questioned using a self-administered questionnaire. Descriptive statistical analysis techniques were used to examine the data. The findings show that when people are motivated, it dramatically increases both their effectiveness and efficiency for attaining corporate objectives.

Statement of the Problem

It seems that a sizable portion of employees today no longer care about their jobs or jobs in general. The failure and subpar performance of businesses are ultimately caused by this lack of motivation. According to Manzoor, Awan, and Mariam (2012), employees in all departments are under a lot of stress, which is hurting their performance as a whole. According to Broni and Nanyele (2012), it might be difficult for managers to get good performance from their staff members in order to meet organizational goals. Managers encounter this difficulty every day. Buchanan's results, which were emphasized in Broni's study (2012), indicate that organizational psychologists have been working hard for at least 50 years to comprehend the connection between motivation and job performance. Therefore the researcher has stated his problem as "Motivation and its Impact on Employee Performance".

Significance of the Study

Due to intense rivalry on a global scale, the research is very important to the companies. Organizations from all around the globe are competing for the limited resources, such personnel. Therefore, they want their company to have a strong reputation for keeping and inspiring workers in order to obtain the correct amount

of employees. To call the organization's attention to the welfare and interests of its personnel so that it will show in the delivery of public services. The research explained motivation's significance to the organization and its meaning. It also emphasized the worth and significance of workers to the growth of the company.

OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the study are as follows-

- To find out the impact of motivation on employee performance
- To study the types of motivation given to the employees

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey design is used in this investigation. Its nature is cross-sectional, qualitative, and qualitative.

Population

Population of this is comprised of the private employees working in different private sectors.

Sample

Out of the selected population the researcher has selected 25 private employees following the random sampling method.

Research Instruments

This study's main data was gathered by questionnaire. Given that the research is concerned with factors that cannot be seen, questionnaires are utilized since they are the most effective approach to gather data. Descriptive analysis is used to get the information. Data from the research area was gathered, edited, collected, and tallied. A five-point Likert scale consisting of 10 items is used to evaluate the motivation level of the respondents. Another semi structured questionnaire entitled Employee Productivity consisting of 12 items of five point likert scale is used to measure the performance of the employees.

Data Analysis

SPSS statistical software was used to tabulate and cross-tabulate the data. Collected data are analyzed with descriptive statistics and Pearson Correlation Coefficient. After analyzing the frequency tables, the researcher came up with a summary of her findings, recommendations, and conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Analysis Interpretation and Presentation

From the table it is clear that the mean score for the employees motivation is 35.6 with the minimum range of 12 and maximum score of 48. The table also shows the SD score 11.394 where as the std Error mean is 2.278 with the variance of 129.833.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for the motivation of the employees

N	25
Minimum	12
Maximum	48
Mean	35.6
Median	38
Mode	46
SD	11.394
Std Error Mean	2.278
Skewness	-0.907
kurtosis	2.970
Variance	129.833

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for work performance of the employees

N	25
Minimum	14
Maximum	56
Mean	40.88
Median	42
Mode	42
SD	11.300
Std Error Mean	2.260
Skewness	-0.729
kurtosis	3.702
Variance	127.693

From the above table, it is clear that the mean score for the employees motivation is 40.88 with the minimum range of 14 and maximum score of 56. The table also shows the SD score 11.300 where as the std Error mean is 2.260 with the variance of 127.693.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Coefficient between the motivation and Performance among private bank employees

Pearson Correlation Coefficient®	0.807
P value	0.000
Covariance	103.908
N	25
Statistic	6.553

The above table indicates that there is a significant large positive relationship between motivation and performance among the private employees of the bank sector, $(r(23) = 0.807, p < .001)$

Discussion

From the data analysis it has been clear that the mean score for both the variable is higher than the average level which indicate the fact that most of the

respondents motivation boosts the work performance of the employees. The study also suggests that there is significant relationship between the motivation and the performance of the employees stressing the fact how important employee motivation is to the growth of the company. This suggests that employee performance is significantly influenced by motivation.

Findings

- The findings showed that motivation, which may be either monetary or non-monetary, is a key factor in any organization’s performance.
- There is significant relationship between the motivation and the performance of the employees
- Motivation can have highly impact on the performance of the Employees.

CONCLUSION

Motivation affects workers; depending on the needs of the employer, motivation may have a positive or negative influence on the worker. The study found that employee performance and satisfaction are significantly influenced by motivation. Employee motivation has many different facets, and financial benefits, which include both internal and external incentives, are only one. Organizations should motivate employees individually rather than as a group since individual employee expectations vary from those of a group. One of management’s most important duties is to make sure that employee work is more meaningful and to balance employee motivation with organizational goals.

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